

The effect of extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, emotional stability and openness to experience towards learning orientation, performance orientation and job performance

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to examine and analyze: 1) the effect of extraversion on learning orientation; 2) The effect of agreeableness on learning orientation; 3) The effect of conscientiousness on learning orientation; 4) The influence of conscientiousness on performance orientation; 5) The influence of emotional stability on performance orientation; 6) The effect of openness to experience on learning orientation; 7) The effect of learning orientation on job performance; 8) The effect of performance orientation on job performance. A total of 306 employees of PT IMS Madiun, Indonesia were used as samples in this study, and the data obtained were processed using the Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) equation model. The findings are:

- The extraversion variable had a positive and significant effect on learning orientation
- The agreeableness variable does not have a significant effect on learning orientation
- Conscientiousness variable has a positive and significant influence on learning orientation
- Conscientiousness variable has a positive and significant effect on performance orientation
- Emotional stability variable has a positive and significant influence on performance orientation
- The openness to experience variable has a positive and significant influence on learning orientation
- The learning orientation variable has a positive and significant effect on job performance
- The performance orientation variable has a positive and significant effect on job performance.

Keywords: Agreeableness; Conscientiousness; Emotional Stability; Extraversion; Job Performance; Learning Orientation; Openness to Experience

1. Introduction

Human resources are the most important factor in a company that will determine the success or failure of the company to achieve common goals within the organization. Human resources are the company's most valuable assets, whose needs must be met properly and owned by an organization, because the key to success in organizations is largely determined by the human element. Qualified human resources are needed by every company. One sign that quality human resources can be observed from the resulting performance. As it is known that employee performance greatly affects the level of success in a company.

A person's performance itself is influenced by three things: ability, desire and environment. Thus, in order for individuals to have good performance, they must understand how to do the job properly, have a high desire and a supportive work environment. Individual abilities and desires are related to a person's personality traits. The

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incompatibility of a person's personality with the work that is his duty will result in losses for the company and the employees themselves.

In this regard, this study was conducted by adopting the conceptual framework model of the research conducted by [1] regarding individual performance which is influenced by personality factors in the perspective of motivation theory, but in this study using the perspective of Human Relationship Theory. The reason for using the perspective of Human Relationship Theory, which was pioneered by Elton Mayo, is because the theory of human relations focuses on paying attention to human elements (leadership attention, generating a sense of belonging, a sense of solidarity in organizations, informal associations). All of these things will make a group of people excited, aware of their life goals, able to show cooperation among members.

In the human element, there is also an essential meaning in a relationship, namely the spiritual process that is focused on happiness based on character, nature, personality, behavioral attitudes and other psychological aspects contained in humans and this can affect human attitudes at work. This kind of understanding can be applied and can be the reason why the spiritual needs of humans in the company need attention, because with the fulfilment of these needs it will be easy for the leadership to direct subordinates to work together and the process of integrating people into a work situation that is conducive to work will occur conducive, this condition will cause individual performance to increase.

Human relations in organizational/institutional management activities, in principle creates a collaboration between employees in a work team, increases productivity, and gains job satisfaction. One of the spiritual processes in human relations is related to one's personality. A person's personality is a unique combination of psychological traits that influence how a person reacts and interacts with others [2]. One of the personality trait theories that is often used in the world of work is the "Big Five Model" or "Big Five Personality Traits Model" proposed by [3], consisting of five key dimensions: Openness to experience, Conscientiousness, Extraversion, Agreeableness and Neuroticism (OCEAN).

In his book [4] entitled "The Revised NEO Personality Inventory" describes the five personalities in the Big Five Personality Traits Model as follows: Openness to experience is defined as a person who is open to things. -new thing; conscientiousness is defined as a person who has a careful nature; extraversion is defined as a person who is easy to socialize, lives in groups; agreeableness is defined as an individual who likes to avoid conflict; and neuroticism is defined as an individual who is able to deal with stress.

A company, if the individuals in it have five positive personalities such as the concept of the Big Five Personality Traits Model, it will cause them to always want to learn continuously, there is a process of developing individual abilities (learning orientation). Another impact of the positive Big Five Personality Traits Model concept causes each individual to have a performance orientation, which means that the nature of comparing himself with others, he is more competent than others. In a company, if the members with self-awareness have an orientation to learning and orientation to performance, it will cause the performance of members to also improve, and this will clearly benefit the company, because human resource management is carried out as a whole. In line with previous study on the concept of personality and overall performance, conducted by [1] who examined the mediating effect of mastering orientation and overall performance orientation on overall performance with personality traits as the independent variable. The result states that motivation which consists of learning and performance orientation has an effect on the main manager's performance. In addition, this study found that there is a relationship between personality and motivation, including extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, and emotional stability, which have a significant relationship with the concept of motivation in performance orientation. While the other two personalities have a significant relationship with the two concepts of motivation, namely learning and performance orientation.

Another study on personality associated with performance is entitled Personality and Job Performance: Test of the Mediating Effects of Motivation Among Sales Representatives [5]. Almost the same as previous studies, but this study looks at the concept of motivation from the side of communion striving, status striving and accomplishment striving, which focuses more on social interaction, in accordance with the object of research, namely sales force. The results show that status striving and accomplishment striving mediate the effects of extraversion and conscientiousness on salesperson performance. This study also shows that although agreeableness is closely related to communion striving, in the end agreeableness also affects salesperson performance, although indirectly.

The replication of the model with a conceptual framework that uses the perspective of Human Relationship Theory will be tested on employees of PT IMS Madiun with the consideration that the company is the only manufacturing company engaged in the railroad industry in Indonesia. PT IMS Madiun is currently transferring the production process from the parent company to the subsidiary, where the production process is no longer carried out by the parent company but is carried out by the subsidiary. The parent company, in this case PT IMS Madiun, only carries out managerial activities.

For this reason, it is important to have good human relationships with employees, so that coordination between the parent company and subsidiaries can run well.

2. Literature Review and Hypothesis Development

Employee Human Relationship Theory was put forward by Elton Mayo in 1949. Elton Mayo concluded that an employee's work productivity is not determined by the conditions of the workplace, the light factor and the amount of wages, but by how an organization provides opportunities for its members to carry out human relations within the organization. This theory prioritizes a person's relationship with his environment. According to this theory, a person will perform well if he is accepted and recognized in his work and environment. Human elements need to be considered, for example the leadership's attention to workers, generating a sense of belonging as a member of the company, a sense of solidarity in organizational life, informal relationships and so on.

Human relations emphasize interactions that are mutually constructive, motivates and creates a conducive atmosphere at work. In this theory, Mayo also argues that employee productivity is not only built on logical and rational arrangements, but the fact that providing emotional and motivational responses through interactions between humans is much more important for increasing employee productivity. According to Mayo, humane treatment of employees and showing appreciation will benefit the company not in the short term but in the long term. Employee involvement in the decision-making process will be more effective in improving the company's progress than just providing rewards.

When a person interacts with the environment or with other individuals, each brings a trait or personality that is a unique characteristic. The discussion of this research uses individual traits in the form of extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, emotional stability and openness to experience which are used as the basis for how each member of the organization conducts positive interactions, fosters constructive motivation, in the end it will create conducive company conditions to increase employee productivity. The motivation used in this research is learning and performance orientation. When employees have both of these motivations, namely the motivation to be learning-oriented and show an orientation to good performance, it will certainly produce good job performance.

Employees who have an extraversion personality tendency are characterized by enthusiasm and enthusiasm in carrying out their activities. Extravert employees are passionate about building relationships with other people or their co-workers, never hesitate to get to know each other and actively make new friends. This enthusiasm is reflected in the emission of positive emotions, a firm and assertive attitude. In addition, employees with extraverted personalities can position themselves well and usually employees with this personality type are able to become leaders in an organization. According to [6], extravert personality is an attitude that is active, affectionate, likes to have fun and talks a lot to get lots of friends.

Agreeableness personality is one part of the Big Five Theory of Personality, where agreeableness describes a person's personality who is kind, cooperative, and full of trust. Agreeableness has characteristics in the form of sincerity in sharing, smoothness of feelings, focus on positive things in others. In everyday life, individuals with agreeableness personality appear as individuals who are kind, cooperative, and trustworthy. In addition, individuals with agreeableness personality are pleasant individuals characterized as forgiving, helpful, soft-hearted, frank, and trusting [6].

Conscientiousness personality is a personality with individual characteristics with the nature of being serious in carrying out tasks, being responsible, reliable, and liking order and discipline. In everyday life, this individual is able to appear as someone who is present on time, accomplished, meticulous, and likes to do homework. Employees who have a conscientiousness personality can be relied on in carrying out their work. According to [6], individuals who have a conscientiousness personality have or have a strong determination, have clear goals, think systematically, and are strong willed in facing challenges. In this study, the conscientiousness indicator was measured using six indicators, namely: efficient, organized, planful, reliable, responsible and thorough [7].

Emotional stability is the emotional stability that individuals have at work. The opposite of emotional stability is neuroticism or anxious nature or individuals who often feel anxious in dealing with something. The nature of neuroticism is synonymous with the presence of negative emotions such as worry, tension, and fear. A person who is dominantly anxious is easily nervous in dealing with problems that most people think are trivial. Individuals will easily become angry when faced with situations that are not in accordance with what they want. In general, individuals will have less tolerance for disappointment and conflict. This condition will be different from emotional stability personality, where individuals who have high emotional stability tend to be calm, strong, relaxed, safe, self-satisfied and not emotional. Individuals with low levels of emotional stability will be susceptible to psychological pressure, individuals

will become someone who is easily anxious, nervous, tends to be emotional, does not have confidence and always feels dissatisfied [6].

Openness to revel in which may be interpreted as openness. This dimension is intently related to the openness of insight and originality of ideas that individuals have in carrying out their work. Individuals who are open are ready to accept various existing stimuli with an open perspective because of their broad insight. According to [6], states that openness to experience is an individual who has an open attitude towards experience, dares to accept challenges. Individuals who have a personality like this have a high curiosity, are creative, imaginative and modern. Individuals with an openness to experience personality will feel active and creative in carrying out their duties and dare to take challenges in their work.

Learning orientation or learning orientation is a learning process from employees as an adjustment effect that affects the relationship between a system and its external environment. Individuals who have a high Learning Orientation then the goal is to increase competence. According to [8], someone who has a learning orientation in his work will have a shared vision, openness or openness to criticism, clear system thinking or systematic thinking, and dissemination of knowledge or always want to share knowledge. Learning orientation can also be interpreted as a situation where individuals try to improve their competence, understand or master something new [9]. In this study, the indicators used to measure learning orientation include: having a strong desire to improve skills, having a strong desire to master skills, having a strong desire to continuously improve abilities, achieving achievement as an opportunity to improve competence. and likes challenges [10].

Performance orientation has the aim of getting a positive assessment and avoiding a negative competency assessment. This will be marked by the nature that is always mastery oriented, likes challenges (seek challenges), is persistent and resilient (high persistence). According to [9], individuals who have a performance orientation survive only if they see themselves as highly skilled. From an organizational point of view, performance orientation tends to lead to short-term results, or the achievement of predetermined work targets, for example, employees have achieved monthly targets set by the company. Performance orientation can be measured using the following indicators: focusing on good performance, seeing good performance as a way to get extrinsic rewards from others, concerned with being judged-able, proving ability with success [10].

The conceptual framework in this study explains the Big Five Personality Traits Model in influencing learning orientation, performance orientation and job performance at PT IMS Madiun employees. The conceptual framework in this study is described as follows:

Source: designed by Authors

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework

2.1. Hypothesis of Research

Based on the conceptual framework in the picture above, the hypothesis in this study is as follows:

- H1: There is an influence between extraversion on the learning orientation.
- H2: There is an influence between agreeableness on the learning orientation.
- H3: There is an influence between conscientiousness on the learning orientation.
- H4: There is an influence between conscientiousness on the performance orientation.
- H5: There is an influence between emotional stability on the performance orientation.
- H6: There is an influence between openness to experience on the learning orientation.
- H7: There is an influence between learning orientation on the job performance.
- H8: There is an influence between performance orientations on the job performance.

3. Methodology

This is quantitative studies. Quantitative studies are studies that is used to take a look at a specific population or sample, Sampling techniques are normally accomplished randomly, the use of studies gear for statistics series, quantitative/statistical evaluation, and the motive is to test predetermined hypotheses [11].

The population in this study were 1,304 employees at PT IMS Madiun spread over 5 divisions, with the criteria that these employees were employees of a certain time contract (PKWT). The divisions taken as the population in this study are 281 employees of fabrication, 554 employees of finishing, 101 employees of quality control, 183 employees of PPC, and 185 employees of components, accessories & interior panel production. Given the relatively large population, in this study the data analysis used a sample with the Slovin formula as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{(1 + Ne^2)}$$

Where:

- n = number of samples
- N = total population
- e = error rate in sampling
- So, by using the Slovin formula, the number of samples that will be used in this study is:
- $n = N / ((1 + Ne^2))$
- $n = 1.304 / ((1 + 1.304 ([0,05]^2)))$
- $n = 306$

This study uses 306 samples of employees of PT IMS Madiun which will be taken from 5 divisions in the company.

This study consists of 8 variables to be studied, namely the independent variables consisting of: extraversion (X1), agreeableness (X2), conscientious (X3), emotional stability (X4), openness to experience (X5), the mediation variables consisting of: learning orientation (Z1) and performance orientation (Z2) and the dependent variable: job performance (Y).

Operational definitions of variables in this study are as follows:

3.1.1. Extraversion

An extravert is someone who is active, loving, fun-loving and talkative [6]. Indicators: active, assertive, energetic, enthusiastic, outgoing and talkative [7].

3.1.2. Agreeableness

A pleasant individual characterized as forgiving, helpful, soft-hearted, frank, and trusting [6]. Indicators: appreciative, forgiving, generous, kind, sympathetic and trusting [7].

3.1.3. *Conscientiousness*

Reflects individuals who have strong determination, have clear goals, think systematically, and are strong willed [6]. Indicators: efficient, organized, planful, reliable, responsible and thorough [7].

3.1.4. *Emotional stability*

Someone who has high emotional stability tends to be calm, strong, relaxed, safe, self-satisfied and unemotional. Individuals with low levels of emotional stability will be vulnerable to psychological pressure, they will become someone who is easily anxious, nervous, tends to be emotional, does not have confidence and always feels dissatisfied [6]. Indicators: anxious, self-pitying, tense, touchy, unstable and worrying [7].

3.1.5. *Openness to experience*

An individual who has an open attitude towards experience, dares to accept challenges. Individuals who have this kind of personality have a high curiosity, are creative, imaginative and modern [6]. Indicators: artistic, curious, imaginative, insightful, original and wide interests [7].

3.1.6. *Learning orientation*

A situation in which individuals try to improve their competence, understand or master new things [9]. Indicators: have a strong desire to improve skills, have a strong desire to master skills, have a strong desire to continuously improve skills, reaching achievements as an opportunity to improve competence and likes challenges [10].

3.1.7. *Performance orientation*

Circumstances in which individuals seek to obtain a favourable assessment of their competence or avoid negative assessments of their competence [9]. Indicators: focus on good performance, sees good performance as a way to gain extrinsic rewards from others, concerned with being judged-able and proving ability with success [10].

3.1.8. *Job Performance*

Performance is a set of outcomes completed and refers back to the act of achieving and carrying out a requested task [12]. Indicators: quality, quantity, punctuality, effectiveness, independence and work commitment.

This study uses primary data, namely data taken directly by researchers from data sources, in this case the data sources are respondents from employees of PT IMS Madiun. Data collection techniques in this study were collected using a questionnaire. The questionnaire in this study was conducted using an online method, namely by utilizing Google Form which was then distributed to respondents and distributed directly to research respondents.

Figure 2 Relationship between Variables and Indicators in the PLS Model

The research instrument used in the study was a questionnaire consisting of closed statements to reveal the variables studied. Ordinal scale is used to provide value information on answers. Each research variable was measured using a

measuring instrument in the form of an ordinal scale questionnaire that met the statements of the Likert Scale type. This indicator is used as a starting point for compiling instrument items which can be in the form of statements or questions, with answer intervals of 1 to 5 by adjusting the questions asked. The following is the answer interval and the score given for each statement item is as follows: Strongly agree, score = 5; Agree, score = 4; Neutral, score = 3; Disagree, score = 2; strongly disagree, score = 1.

In this study, the collected data were analyzed using structural equation modelling (SEM) Partial Least Square (PLS).

4. Data Analysis

4.1. Research Model Testing (Outer Model / Measurement Model)

The research model that has been formed needs to be tested to prove the quality of the model related to the variables and constructs, based on the value of the research data obtained. Data analysis using SmartPLS, model testing is also called testing/assessing the Outer Model (the relationship between the latent variable and its manifest variable). There are three test criteria to be carried out on the model, namely the model validity test with convergent validity and discriminant validity, and the model reliability test with composite reliability.

4.1.1. Convergent Validity

Convergent validity is one of the validity tests of the research model carried out by measuring reflective indicators (indicators are seen as the effects of observable/measured constructs), which are assessed based on the correlation between item scores/component scores. Individual reflective measures are stated to be high if they correlate greater than 0.70 with the assemble being measured. but, according to [13] for studies in the early levels of developing a size scale, the loading fee of 0.5 to zero.6 is taken into consideration enough. In this study, the minimum limit of the loading factor value of 0.60 will be used:

Table 1 Outer loading result

	X1	X2	X3	X4	X5	Z1	Z2	Y
X1_1	0.750							
X1_2	0.649							
X1_3	0.751							
X1_5	0.748							
X1_6	0.678							
X1_7	0.798							
X1_8	0.757							
X1_9	0.698							
X1_10	0.798							
X1_11	0.689							
X1_12	0.763							
X2_1		0.648						
X2_2		0.687						
X2_4		0.746						
X2_6		0.742						
X2_7		0.690						
X2_8		0.702						
X2_9		0.716						

X2_10		0.759					
X2_11		0.734					
X2_12		0.808					
X3_1			0.668				
X3_3			0.744				
X3_4			0.815				
X3_5			0.783				
X3_6			0.689				
X3_7			0.792				
X3_8			0.765				
X3_9			0.806				
X3_10			0.740				
X3_11			0.753				
X3_12			0.765				
X4_1				0.665			
X4_2				0.695			
X4_3				0.643			
X4_4				0.724			
X4_5				0.800			
X4_6				0.773			
X4_7				0.766			
X4_8				0.742			
X4_9				0.758			
X4_10				0.826			
X4_11				0.790			
X4_12				0.677			
X5_1					0.805		
X5_2					0.779		
X5_3					0.762		
X5_4					0.795		
X5_5					0.733		
X5_6					0.791		
X5_7					0.811		
X5_8					0.783		
X5_9					0.716		
X5_10					0.704		
X5_11					0.821		
X5_12					0.802		

Y_1								0.841
Y_2								0.790
Y_3								0.832
Y_4								0.830
Y_5								0.755
Y_6								0.840
Y_7								0.838
Y_8								0.742
Y_9								0.841
Y_10								0.790
Y_11								0.832
Y_12								0.830
Z1_1						0.758		
Z1_2						0.739		
Z1_3						0.753		
Z1_4						0.848		
Z1_5						0.816		
Z1_6						0.801		
Z1_7						0.793		
Z1_8						0.814		
Z1_9						0.807		
Z1_10						0.809		
Z2_1							0.790	
Z2_2							0.837	
Z2_3							0.778	
Z2_4							0.818	
Z2_5							0.804	
Z2_6							0.826	
Z2_7							0.751	
Z2_8							0.782	

Source: processed field data with SmartPLS

Based on the table above, it is known that all indicators have a loading factor value of more than 0.6. From the table above, it is also known that the most dominant indicator influencing job performance variables is related to being able to organize their own work properly according to the target. While the indicators that are considered to need to be improved are related to being fully aware of their responsibilities at work.

4.1.2. Discriminant Validity

Discriminant Validity is also a test of the validity of the research model with SmartPLS. Discriminant Validity describes the ability of each indicator to make a distinction between its construct and other constructs. The model is said to be valid if the value of each indicator in the construct has the greatest factor loading value when connected to other constructs. The outcomes of the discriminant validity check are obtained as follows.

Table 2 Discriminant Validity Value (Cross Loading)

	X1	X2	X3	X4	X5	Z1	Z2	Y
X1_1	0.750	0.447	0.493	0.563	0.456	0.474	0.381	0.409
X1_2	0.798	0.530	0.569	0.663	0.525	0.540	0.423	0.489
X1_3	0.689	0.453	0.443	0.501	0.429	0.414	0.347	0.418
X1_5	0.763	0.591	0.595	0.611	0.491	0.545	0.492	0.544
X1_6	0.649	0.544	0.542	0.495	0.526	0.503	0.468	0.480
X1_7	0.751	0.535	0.567	0.595	0.516	0.521	0.418	0.502
X1_8	0.748	0.581	0.569	0.682	0.561	0.582	0.522	0.529
X1_9	0.678	0.573	0.578	0.520	0.509	0.510	0.544	0.543
X1_10	0.798	0.564	0.534	0.535	0.562	0.546	0.474	0.516
X1_11	0.757	0.528	0.518	0.515	0.520	0.504	0.451	0.462
X1_12	0.698	0.498	0.471	0.505	0.495	0.496	0.362	0.410
X2_1	0.417	0.648	0.501	0.420	0.420	0.406	0.460	0.401
X2_2	0.506	0.759	0.591	0.479	0.541	0.503	0.494	0.512
X2_4	0.547	0.734	0.662	0.551	0.511	0.549	0.507	0.583
X2_6	0.543	0.808	0.683	0.528	0.625	0.579	0.546	0.541
X2_7	0.419	0.687	0.520	0.400	0.518	0.494	0.543	0.498
X2_8	0.550	0.746	0.583	0.549	0.527	0.536	0.522	0.547
X2_9	0.479	0.742	0.564	0.469	0.575	0.570	0.549	0.521
X2_10	0.534	0.690	0.537	0.570	0.485	0.502	0.478	0.523
X2_11	0.589	0.702	0.624	0.560	0.512	0.505	0.443	0.488
X2_12	0.658	0.716	0.626	0.562	0.531	0.524	0.470	0.488
X3_1	0.500	0.632	0.668	0.543	0.560	0.555	0.492	0.503
X3_3	0.512	0.679	0.740	0.558	0.625	0.621	0.623	0.608
X3_4	0.538	0.592	0.753	0.611	0.549	0.554	0.552	0.592
X3_5	0.519	0.608	0.765	0.555	0.606	0.547	0.534	0.538
X3_6	0.679	0.643	0.744	0.660	0.659	0.642	0.527	0.587
X3_7	0.588	0.645	0.815	0.578	0.630	0.665	0.532	0.601
X3_8	0.512	0.635	0.783	0.543	0.649	0.610	0.582	0.591
X3_9	0.399	0.417	0.589	0.477	0.413	0.466	0.389	0.397
X3_10	0.546	0.598	0.792	0.625	0.545	0.632	0.536	0.612
X3_11	0.623	0.598	0.765	0.642	0.582	0.631	0.531	0.591
X3_12	0.573	0.645	0.806	0.575	0.565	0.597	0.587	0.630
X4_1	0.504	0.615	0.607	0.665	0.566	0.541	0.488	0.497
X4_2	0.592	0.473	0.549	0.826	0.496	0.518	0.395	0.457
X4_3	0.632	0.480	0.549	0.790	0.532	0.594	0.410	0.495

X4_4	0.466	0.393	0.405	0.677	0.380	0.473	0.324	0.376
X4_5	0.476	0.362	0.411	0.695	0.371	0.427	0.287	0.344
X4_6	0.419	0.461	0.468	0.643	0.498	0.481	0.459	0.431
X4_7	0.591	0.550	0.604	0.724	0.586	0.601	0.517	0.531
X4_8	0.590	0.438	0.541	0.800	0.495	0.526	0.391	0.481
X4_9	0.711	0.583	0.619	0.773	0.577	0.581	0.477	0.533
X4_10	0.572	0.536	0.615	0.766	0.548	0.546	0.451	0.523
X4_11	0.618	0.645	0.702	0.742	0.625	0.633	0.635	0.663
X4_12	0.564	0.524	0.608	0.758	0.570	0.580	0.508	0.565
X5_1	0.592	0.572	0.621	0.604	0.805	0.677	0.560	0.555
X5_2	0.559	0.517	0.610	0.642	0.704	0.678	0.490	0.580
X5_3	0.528	0.591	0.627	0.568	0.821	0.746	0.607	0.596
X5_4	0.468	0.569	0.565	0.455	0.802	0.688	0.618	0.587
X5_5	0.509	0.548	0.552	0.525	0.779	0.615	0.520	0.529
X5_6	0.508	0.470	0.518	0.482	0.762	0.571	0.501	0.521
X5_7	0.508	0.608	0.635	0.511	0.795	0.641	0.591	0.556
X5_8	0.568	0.509	0.606	0.621	0.733	0.659	0.478	0.579
X5_9	0.582	0.564	0.632	0.631	0.791	0.726	0.546	0.577
X5_10	0.544	0.579	0.580	0.553	0.811	0.680	0.579	0.595
X5_11	0.530	0.652	0.646	0.538	0.783	0.658	0.632	0.577
X5_12	0.555	0.586	0.639	0.584	0.716	0.615	0.549	0.568
Y_1	0.555	0.601	0.651	0.532	0.602	0.641	0.723	0.746
Y_2	0.583	0.576	0.664	0.632	0.587	0.690	0.625	0.840
Y_3	0.590	0.611	0.629	0.624	0.641	0.683	0.684	0.838
Y_4	0.405	0.540	0.526	0.429	0.550	0.563	0.626	0.742
Y_5	0.538	0.572	0.620	0.522	0.584	0.630	0.696	0.795
Y_6	0.503	0.533	0.567	0.559	0.572	0.645	0.611	0.774
Y_7	0.521	0.515	0.573	0.577	0.553	0.634	0.562	0.764
Y_8	0.520	0.548	0.590	0.495	0.520	0.584	0.648	0.841
Y_9	0.477	0.520	0.584	0.491	0.581	0.584	0.671	0.790
Y_10	0.535	0.587	0.631	0.539	0.633	0.657	0.708	0.832
Y_11	0.536	0.625	0.671	0.572	0.651	0.676	0.743	0.830
Y_12	0.513	0.510	0.561	0.568	0.515	0.629	0.548	0.755
Z1_1	0.488	0.551	0.599	0.548	0.724	0.758	0.580	0.570
Z1_2	0.562	0.517	0.610	0.570	0.705	0.809	0.599	0.631
Z1_3	0.597	0.557	0.624	0.658	0.579	0.739	0.463	0.590
Z1_4	0.431	0.561	0.601	0.553	0.648	0.753	0.548	0.553
Z1_5	0.635	0.672	0.718	0.674	0.733	0.848	0.630	0.707

Z1_6	0.559	0.580	0.652	0.598	0.650	0.816	0.579	0.660
Z1_7	0.578	0.587	0.608	0.555	0.769	0.801	0.611	0.646
Z1_8	0.569	0.552	0.617	0.611	0.625	0.793	0.551	0.641
Z1_9	0.532	0.578	0.635	0.529	0.681	0.814	0.602	0.673
Z1_10	0.599	0.536	0.640	0.632	0.692	0.807	0.587	0.655
Z2_1	0.470	0.533	0.579	0.479	0.557	0.555	0.790	0.631
Z2_2	0.520	0.626	0.639	0.536	0.608	0.623	0.837	0.721
Z2_3	0.516	0.566	0.574	0.471	0.602	0.589	0.778	0.638
Z2_4	0.530	0.588	0.607	0.535	0.547	0.567	0.818	0.706
Z2_5	0.470	0.563	0.583	0.509	0.556	0.583	0.804	0.622
Z2_6	0.436	0.533	0.553	0.502	0.592	0.594	0.826	0.606
Z2_7	0.750	0.447	0.493	0.563	0.456	0.474	0.381	0.409
Z2_8	0.798	0.530	0.569	0.663	0.525	0.540	0.423	0.489

Source: processed field data with SmartPLS

From the table above, it can be seen that the value of each indicator in the construct has the greatest factor loading value when associated with other constructs which means that each latent variable has appropriate discriminant validity or it can be said that the research model can be declared valid.

4.1.3. Composite Reliability and Average Variance Extracted

After all cross loadings output values meet the validity test requirements (having the largest factor loading value), the next step is to carry out a reliability test on the research model. Reliability testing related to the outer model uses composite reliability. Composite reliability aims to test the value of the reliability of the indicators in a construct. A construct (latent variable and manifest variable) is said to meet composite reliability (reliable) if it has a composite reliability value > 0.7 and the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value of each construct is required > 0.50 . The following are the composite reliability and average variance extracted values for each construct:

Table 3 Composite Reliability and Average Variance Extracted

Variables	Composite Reliability	AVE	Remark
Extraversion	0.928327	0.541748	Reliable
Agreeableness	0.916718	0.524827	Reliable
Conscientiousness	0.933427	0.562104	Reliable
Emotional stability	0.935412	0.548271	Reliable
Openness to experience	0.947696	0.602119	Reliable
Learning orientation	0.944705	0.631163	Reliable
Performance orientation	0.933726	0.638083	Reliable
Job Performance	0.954119	0.634614	Reliable

Source: processed field data with SmartPLS

Based on the table above, it is able to be concluded that every construct meets the dependable criteria that is indicated by means of the composite reliability value above 0.70 as required through the standards. The AVE value for every assemble has a value above 0.50 which means that every variable has a composite reliability value that is sufficient to meet the reliable requirements.

4.2. Structural Model Testing (Inner Model)

Testing of the inner model or structural model is carried out to see the relationship/influence between the independent latent variables and their constructs on the dependent latent variables and their constructs in the research model. The inner model testing is carried out simultaneously (all independent variables together) and partially (individually independent variables).

Simultaneous testing is carried out to determine whether there is an effect of all independent latent variables together on the dependent latent variable. Simultaneous testing uses the significance value and R-Square of the research model. While the partial test was conducted to determine the effect of all independent latent variables individually/independently their influence on the dependent latent variable. The partial test uses the result for inner weight. with a statistical t-test for the significance of the structural path parameter coefficients.

4.2.1. Simultaneous Model Test (R Square)

In testing/assessing the model using PLS simultaneously, it is done by looking at the R-Square (R^2) which aims to test the effect of the exogenous latent variable on the endogenous latent variable. The higher the R-Square (R^2) value, the stronger the influence of the exogenous latent variable on the Endogenous latent variable in the prediction model of the proposed research. The results of the R-square estimation using SmartPLS are presented in the following table.

Table 4 R-Square Value

Variables	R^2	Remark
Learning orientation	0.782	The contribution of the variables of extraversion. Agreeableness. Conscientiousness. And openness to experience on learning orientation is 78.2%.
Performance orientation	0.528	The contribution of conscientiousness and emotional stability variables to performance orientation is 52.8%.
Job performance	0.764	The contribution of learning orientation and performance orientation variables to job performance is 76.4%.

Source: processed field data with SmartPLS

Based on the table above, it shows that the learning orientation variable is influenced by the extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, and openness to experience variables of 0.782 or 78.2%. This means that the variables extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, and openness to experience can influence learning orientation by 78.2%. While the remaining 21.8% is influenced by other variables not examined in this study.

For the performance orientation variable, it is influenced by the conscientiousness and emotional stability variables of 0.528 or 52.8%. This means that the conscientiousness and emotional stability variables are able to influence the performance orientation variable by 52.8%. While the remaining 41.2% is influenced by other variables not examined in this study.

While the job performance variable is influenced by the learning orientation and performance orientation variables by 0.764 or 76.4%. This means that learning orientation and performance orientation variables are able to influence job performance variables by 76.4%. While the remaining 23.6% is influenced by other variables not examined in this study.

4.2.2. Hypothesis Testing (Partial Model Test)

Hypothesis testing is intended to prove the alleged previous research whether it has the truth and consistency with the results. The basis used in testing the hypothesis is the value contained in the output result for inner weight (inner model path coefficients), by comparing t statistics (output analysis) with t tables. or also known as t test. The following are the results of each analysis as presented in the table below which provides an estimated output for testing the structural model.

Hypothesis testing using SmartPLS software statistically for every hypothesized relationship was completed using simulation. In this situation, a bootstrap evaluation was finished on a pattern of 306. Trying out with bootstrap become also meant to decrease the trouble of abnormal studies information. The results of the bootstrapping take a look at from the SmartPLS analysis are as follows:

- Testing the first hypothesis (H1): There is an influence between extraversion on learning orientation. The results of testing the first hypothesis (H1) show that the effect of the extraversion variable on learning orientation shows the path coefficient value (weight of influence) of 0.101 (10.1%) with a T-statistic value of 2.076 which is greater than the T-table value of 1.960. These results mean that extraversion (X1) has a positive and significant effect on learning orientation (Z1), meaning that the first hypothesis (H1) in this study is accepted.
- Testing the second hypothesis (H2): There is an influence between agreeableness on learning orientation. The results of testing the second hypothesis (H2) indicate that the influence of the agreeableness variable on learning orientation shows the path coefficient value (weight of influence) of 0.008 (0.8%) with a T-statistic value of 0.140 which is smaller than the T-table value of 1.960. These results mean that agreeableness (X2) has no significant effect on learning orientation (Z1). meaning that the second hypothesis (H2) in this study was rejected.

Table 5 Result for inner weight

Hypothesis	Influence	Influence Weight	T Statistic	T Table	Remark
H1	X1 → Z1	0.101	2.076	1.96	Significant
H2	X2 → Z1	0.008	0.140	1.96	Not significant
H3	X3 → Z1	0.266	4.182	1.96	Significant
H4	X3 → Z2	0.581	9.430	1.96	Significant
H5	X4 → Z2	0.178	3.047	1.96	Significant
H6	X5 → Z1	0.575	11.126	1.96	Significant
H7	Z1 → Y	0.422	8.647	1.96	Significant
H8	Z2 → Y	0.518	10.872	1.96	Significant

Source: processed field data with SmartPLS

- Testing the third hypothesis (H3): There is an influence between conscientiousness on learning orientation. The results of testing the third hypothesis (H3) show that the influence of the conscientiousness variable on learning orientation shows the path coefficient value (weight of influence) of 0.266 (26.6%) with a T-statistic value of 4.182 which is greater than the T-table value of 1.960. This result means that conscientiousness (X3) has a positive and significant influence on learning orientation (Z1), meaning that the third hypothesis (H3) in this study is accepted.
- Testing the fourth hypothesis (H4): There is an influence between conscientiousness on performance orientation. The results of testing the fourth hypothesis (H4) show that the influence of the conscientiousness variable on performance orientation shows the path coefficient value (weight of influence) of 0.581 (58.1%) with a T-statistic value of 9.430 which is greater than the T-table value of 1.960. This result means that conscientiousness (X3) has a positive and significant influence on performance orientation (Z2), meaning that the fourth hypothesis (H4) in this study is accepted.
- Testing the fifth hypothesis (H5): There is an influence between emotional stability on performance orientation. The results of testing the fifth hypothesis (H5) indicate that the influence of the emotional stability variable on performance orientation shows the path coefficient value (weight of influence) of 0.178 (17.8%) with a T-statistic value of 3.047 which is greater than the T-table value of 1.960. These results mean that emotional stability (X4) has a positive and significant effect on performance orientation (Z2), meaning that the fifth hypothesis (H5) in this study is accepted.
- Testing the sixth hypothesis (H6): There is an influence between openness to experience on learning orientation. The results of testing the sixth hypothesis (H6) show that the influence of the openness to experience variable on learning orientation shows the path coefficient value (weight of influence) of 0.575 (57.5%) with a T-statistic value of 11.126 which is greater than the T-table value of 1.960. This result means that openness to experience (X5) has a positive and significant effect on learning orientation (Z1), meaning that the sixth hypothesis (H6) in this study is accepted.
- Testing the seventh hypothesis (H7): There is an influence between learning orientation on job performance. The results of testing the seventh hypothesis (H7) show that the influence of the learning orientation variable on job performance shows the path coefficient value (weight of influence) of 0.422 (42.2%) with a T-statistic

value of 8.647 greater than the T-table value of 1.960. These results mean that learning orientation (Z1) has a positive and significant effect on job performance (Y), meaning that the seventh hypothesis (H7) in this study is accepted.

Testing the eighth hypothesis (H8): There is an influence between performance orientations on job performance. The results of testing the eighth hypothesis (H8) show that the influence of the performance orientation variable on job performance shows the path coefficient value (weight of influence) of 0.518 (51.8%) with a T-statistic value of 10.872 which is greater than the T-table value of 1.960. These results mean that performance orientation (Z2) has a positive and significant effect on job performance (Y), meaning that the eighth hypothesis (H8) in this study is accepted.

5. Discussion

5.1. The Effect of Extraversion on Learning Orientation

The results of this study provide information that the extraversion personality of PT IMS Madiun employees has an impact on learning orientation, where the more employees who have an extraversion personality, the higher the learning orientation. To increase the extraversion personality of employee's management needs to increase employee enthusiasm in interacting with other people, in this case stakeholders from the company. Attitudes in the form of employee enthusiasm in interacting with other people are the indicators that contribute the most in shaping the extraversion personality character. This is in accordance with the existing conditions. Where this company has many relationships or work partners who need communication in their business activities. To support this interaction activity. Employees with extraversion personality are needed. The results of this study support the theory put forward by [14], which states that individuals with extraversion tend to like activities so they can interact socially. High scores on this dimension indicate individuals who are active, friendly, optimistic and vocal. Making it easier for individuals to develop in their environment. Likewise, employees who have an extraversion personality tend to easily do learning orientation while enjoying the process of approaching their work environment. According to [6] the extraversion dimension is described as a set of traits that are closely related to a person's positive emotions such as joy and pleasure. In addition, this dimension relates to the ability to socialize, energetic, active and others. which also show interest in the role of personality in processes and activities for learning. Extraversion individuals really enjoy their activities and interpret them as a medium to meet many people and establish communication with each other. It was further explained that it makes sense when extraversion individuals tend to have a willingness to learn and face the challenges that surround them. In addition, the extraversion personality leads to the desire for positive activities and prioritizes excitement seeking in life [6].

5.2. The Effect of Agreeableness on Learning Orientation

The results showed that agreeableness did not have a significant effect on learning orientation, this is in line with the theory proposed by [6]. In his opinion, agreeableness is a dimension that describes as a trait that is almost the same as extraversion. This dimension relates to trusting, sympathetic and cooperative. People who have low agreeableness tend to be cynical, uncaring and antagonistic. A low agreeableness attitude and personality is certainly very detrimental to individuals when they are in a work environment where individuals will be uncomfortable and can damage working conditions in an organization.

Low agreeableness in employees will greatly hinder employee learning orientation activities, so that employee abilities are difficult to develop. In contrast to agreeableness in individuals. it indicates the individual's tendency to be socially adaptable. Likable, friendly and affectionate [14]. High scores on this dimension describe individuals who are full of warmth, gentle heart, sensitive, easy to sympathize, generous, tend to be easy to help, trustworthy and easy to forgive.

In general, related to the description of agreeableness dimensions at PT. IMS Madiun is considered good, but the agreeableness dimension is still not high enough to contribute or play a role in improving employee learning orientation. Agreeableness describes employees who are socially adaptable, warm, and easy to help others. This is contrary to the results of the research hypothesis test because the second hypothesis is rejected. There is no relationship between agreeableness and learning orientation. Private company employees should be able to help their customers, this is because employees with agreeableness will tend to easily empathize, sensitive to customer needs. So, they will try to help customers in choosing and using the products produced by the company.

In addition, other factors that cause the agreeableness variable do not have a significant effect because PT IMS Madiun is a monopoly company in the railroad industry. It is undeniable that competitors make companies work harder to improve the quality of their products. However, the absence of competitors causes the company to run as it is in

accordance with the demand for goods or services needed for the railway industry. These factors make employees able to accept anything given by the company without any desire to improve themselves through the learning process.

According to [15], the existence of agreeableness does not guarantee that the employee is in the learning orientation process. The results showed that strong or weak agreeableness had no effect on learning orientation. The reason agreeableness does not play a role in predicting learning orientation is that there are employee activities that are more directed towards product activities. This causes employees to seem to only carry out routine work that is considered normal without feeling that there are more severe work challenges.

5.3. The Effect of Conscientiousness on Learning Orientation

The results of this study are in line with the theory proposed by [6], that the conscientiousness dimension is a dimension related to being responsible, careful, thorough, organized, reliable, hardworking, self-disciplined, punctual, thorough, neat, ambitious and persistent. However, these personalities are described as more prone to compulsive personality disorder and tendencies to be antisocial. The conscientiousness condition at PT IMS Madiun is considered good or high and this certainly shows that employees have positive traits related to conscientiousness which ultimately gives a positive role to learning orientation.

The results of this study also support the research conducted by [16], that employees who have a high conscientiousness personality have a tendency to try to work wholeheartedly so that it is possible to receive positive feedback that causes the employee to be satisfied with his work. According to research [17], explains that employees who have a high conscientiousness personality have a tendency to work well so they will always evaluate their work so they are satisfied with the work they do. Activities on job evaluation as a form of learning orientation carried out by employees with the aim of improving performance that is felt to be less in accordance with their work needs.

5.4. The Effect of Conscientiousness on Performance Orientation

The results of this study support the theory of [18] which explain that conscientiousness is a personality dimension that concerns the way a person monitor, regulates, and directs impulses. Individuals with a high level of conscientiousness are characterized as responsible, organized, trustworthy, and persistent. Employees with high conscientiousness will play an important role in shaping employee performance orientation. This is in line with the performance theory proposed by [19] that performance can be defined as the outcome or result of a job on the participation of employees in an organization. The characteristics of people who have high performance are as follows: 1) Have high personal responsibility; 2) Dare to take and bear the risks faced; 3) Have realistic goals; 4) Have a comprehensive work plan and strive to realize its goals; 5) Utilizing concrete feedback in all work activities he does; 6) Look for opportunities to realize the plans that have been programmed.

The results of this study also support the theory put forward by [20] that conscientiousness personality is the right predictor for achieving the best performance for all types of work. Personality is a very important aspect of the study of behavior in the organizational environment. Research on personality has found a relationship between personality and employee performance.

5.5. The Effect of Emotional Stability on Performance Orientation

In general, it is known that the emotional stability at PT IMS Madiun is considered good. This means that employees who have high emotional stability tend to be calm, strong, relaxed, safe, self-satisfied and not emotional. Individuals with a high level of emotional stability will have resistance to psychological pressure in carrying out their work. Emotional stability personality has a positive impact on the performance orientation of the company's employees. This is evidenced from the results of statistical calculations proving that the influence of the emotional stability variable on the performance orientation of the company's employees shows a path coefficient value (weight of influence) of 0.178 (17.8%) with a T-statistic value of 3.047 which is greater than the T-table value of 1.960. These results mean that emotional stability has a positive and significant influence on the performance orientation of the company's employees.

5.6. The Effect of Openness to Experience on Learning Orientation

In this study, the personality of openness to experience was measured by the following indicators: artistic, curious, imaginative, insightful, original and wide interests [7]. In general, it is known that the openness to experience at PT IMS Madiun is considered very good. This shows that openness to experience is related to individuals who have an open attitude towards experience, dare to accept challenges. Individuals who have a personality like this have a high curiosity are creative, imaginative and modern are always inherent in employees. Although there are still some shortcomings related to the personality that is openness to experience in employees.

The openness to experience of this company's employees has a positive impact on employee learning orientation. This is evidenced from the results of statistical calculations proving that the effect of the variable openness to experience on the learning orientation of the company's employees shows a path coefficient value (weight of influence) of 0.575 (57.5%) with a T-statistic value of 11.126 which is greater than the T-table value of 1.960. This result means that openness to experience has a positive and significant influence on employee learning orientation.

5.7. The Effect of Learning Orientation on Job Performance

In general, it is known that the learning orientation of employees at PT IMS Madiun is considered good. This shows that the state of employees to try to improve their competence, understand or master something new is considered good and employees have a strong will to be able to develop at work. The personality attitude that the employee's learning orientation has an impact on the employee's job performance. This is evidenced from the results of statistical calculations proving that the influence of the learning orientation variable on the job performance of the company's employees shows a path coefficient value (weight of influence) of 0.422 (42.2%) with a T-statistic value of 8.647 greater than the T-table value. of 1.960. These results mean that learning orientation has a positive and significant effect on employee job performance.

5.8. The Effect of Performance Orientation on Job Performance

In general, it is known that the performance orientation of PT IMS Madiun employees is considered very good. This shows that performance orientation which is related to a situation where individuals try to get a favorable assessment of their competence or avoid negative assessments of their competence can be carried out well. The performance orientation generated by the company's employees has an impact on job performance.

Based on the analysis of the description related to job performance. it shows that there are weaknesses related to the ability of employees to complete work without depending on others (indicator Y_9). This happens because the work system in the company is mostly done with a team work system. So that when employees do work individually, the results of the work produced are felt to be unsatisfactory. For job performance that has gone well. it is related to awareness of responsibility at work (indicator Y_12). The company's employees have reliable performance because employees have a high attitude of responsibility at work. In general, it is known that the job performance of the company's employees is considered very good. This shows that the job performance has met the expectations and targets that have been set.

Based totally at the effects of statistical calculations, it proves that the influence of the performance orientation variable on employee job performance shows a path coefficient value (weight of influence) of 0.518 (51.8%) with a T-Statistic value of 10.872 which is greater than the T-table value of 1.960. These results mean that performance orientation has a positive and significant effect on job performance.

5.9. Managerial Implication

Providing input to the organization/company, through trait analysis, business leaders can get a complete picture of their strengths and weaknesses and understand how their employees perceive the organization. Selecting the right people contributes to organizational effectiveness and allows companies to incorporate personality assessments as a performance appraisal tool. Organizations can identify important characters and traits that reside in certain locations within the organization. Scoring with the trait approach also helps determine whether a leader has the right personality to receive a promotion or placement in a company area. In addition to the process of attracting people to the company, the hiring process can also use a trait approach to see if someone fits the company's needs.

As the data is collected from mostly 'shop floor' workers, the results may need to be interpreted with caution and can be developed at senior management level or in other areas such as sales. This research also provides input to enrich the theory of the relationship between Extraversion, Agreeableness, Conscientiousness, Emotional Stability and Openness to Experience on Learning Orientation, Performance Orientation and Job Performance.

6. Conclusion

Based on the results of data analysis and discussion in the previous chapter, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- The extraversion variable has a positive and significant effect on learning orientation.
- The agreeableness variable has no significant effect on learning orientation.
- Conscientiousness variable has a positive and significant influence on learning orientation.

- Conscientiousness variable has a positive and significant effect on performance orientation.
- Emotional stability variable has a positive and significant influence on performance orientation.
- The openness to experience variable has a positive and significant influence on learning orientation.
- The learning orientation variable has a positive and significant effect on job performance.
- The performance orientation variable has a positive and significant effect on job performance.

Selecting the right people contributes to organizational effectiveness and allows companies to include personality assessment as a performance appraisal tool. Organizations can identify important characters and traits that reside in certain locations within the organization. Scoring with the trait approach also helps determine whether a leader has the right personality to receive a promotion or placement in an area of the company. In addition to the process of attracting people to the company, the hiring process can also use a trait approach to see if someone fits the company's needs.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors wish to declare that none has any interest to disclose.

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